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Blended Learning Strategies in Learner-Centered Classroom: An Overview

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Abstract

Advances in technology have caused changes in English teaching and learning. Technology can be a useful tool for English teachers to facilitate language learning. Although there are different perspectives on the use of technology in education, blended learning (BL) approaches are of interest to language teachers around the world. Blended learning combines traditional face-to-face instruction with online instruction. This study presents findings from the relevant literature on the use of blended learning in terms of what strategies and procedures practitioners have implemented in their research. The literature generally reflects the significant benefits of blended learning in the acquisition and teaching of various language learning skills.

Keywords: *Technology, Blended learning, E learning, Teaching and Learning English, Language skills.*

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Introduction

In this information age, it is critical for teachers to stay up to date and rapidly change curricula to meet learner needs and complex classroom conditions. Traditional teaching is one of the oldest learning strategies. It is a convenient and economical learning strategy for imparting important information and concepts to the large groups of learners. Traditional lecturing methods are called teacher-centered learning strategies, where information is conveyed by the teacher and passively perceived by the learner (Samuelson & park., 2017). The use of modern technology in English language teaching is becoming increasingly important, especially with the introduction of advanced technology in all fields. Nowadays, modern technologies such as smartphones, tablets, and laptops are widely used in English language teaching, facilitating the use of new approaches and techniques in teaching, thereby leading to the achievement of desired educational goals.

Making use of technology in English language teaching provides students with critical thinking and practical components of language and boosts their efficacy in overall teaching and learning (AlQahtani, 2019). Applying modern technology may offer the flexibility to increase learning time and opportunities for language learning (Cummins et al., 2006) as well as help learners engage actively in the language learning. Classroom teaching alone may not be enough to gear towards the learners' educational needs leading to the demand for modern technology to alleviate the problems (Banditvilai, 2016). Additionally, teachers can edit and adapt the materials to meet students' needs and desired learning developments. Blended learning approaches that incorporate digital technology can help teachers introduce and adapt differentiated instruction based on students' varying progress. (Horn & Staker, 2011; Hilliard 2015).

Blended learning approach like many approaches has its own strengths and setbacks. As a new preferred approach in education, integrating online and face-to-face education so that learners get the most benefit from their lessons is a controversial topic. As Bolandifar (2017) pointed out, integrating physical education with technology-enabled instruction and online learning is considered the most preferred 21st century skill in today's classrooms.

Blended learning methods, as a planned and systematic approach, combine the values of both forms of education and at the same time reduce their weaknesses. The strength of this approach lies in the use of promising intercommunication technologies to integrate the best features of face-to-face and online interactions (Abdul Rahman et al., 2020). This approach allows teaching and learning activities to take place not only within the classroom, but also beyond the boundaries of the classroom. The traditional classroom educational experience is enhanced by incorporating online components. The online component is considered a practical solution to the problem of lack of opportunities for learners to communicate their ideas and language. One can observe a wide variety of learning experiences in Blended Learning method such as presentations, workshops, self-paced learning, online interaction, and communication tasks, lectures and the use of mutual multimedia (Draffan & Rainger, 2006).

Blended courses are generally considered learner-centered classes. In other words, it's not just teachers who share information.; it includes students as well (Abdul Rahman et al., 2020). This allows students to engage in their learning consciously and take on greater responsibility, while receiving support and reassurance from the teacher as a facilitator. (Moore et al, 2010). There are many opportunities to take advantage of productive and timely teacher intervention and support, pair and group work, and a large number of input providers in a highly interactive educational environment. Poon (2013) supports the idea that blended learning represents a significant transformation in

education from teacher-centered to learner-centered education. Learners can easily access learning materials anytime, anywhere. This method combines the best aspects of online presentation of material and classroom interaction, resulting in personalization of learning and thoughtful reflection (Watson, 2015).

There are three notions that technology is utilized to advocate them in Blended Learning; traditional didactic, active learning, and interactive learning. Therefore, teachers have access to a variety of techniques that meet the individual needs of language learners (Tawil, 2018). Unlike traditional learning situations where space and time constraints are obvious, it is up to the learner to determine the appropriate context for carrying out the activity. (Keshta & Harb, 2013).

Bu (2019) argues that blended learning approaches can be viewed from different perspectives. The first perspective is to teach a theory that combines cognitivism, behaviorism, and constructivism. According to Aborisade (2013), the use of technological devices allows learners to participate in personalized presentations that stimulate their cognitive skills for knowledge creation, and in this way, teachers can improve learners' cognitive constructivism, thinking patterns, and knowledge concepts can be easily discovered (Tawil, 2018). The second perspective concerns learning styles that combine physical and interactive online learning. This online material is available almost 24 hours a day in parallel with the physical interaction, allowing learners to benefit from additional activities to reinforce what they have learned (O'Donnell, 2006). In this environment, collaboration is expected as teachers act as directors, facilitators, and guides. Teachers guide learners to pay attention to online materials. They identify mistakes that learners make and correct them immediately.

When it comes to educational media, you can see a collection of classic media and advanced educational technology tools. Therefore, Krause (2007) argues that blended learning creates an educational environment that effectively combines different educational platforms and different models of educational approaches. This combination leads to higher-order thinking skills including comparison, classification, induction, deduction, error analysis, support building, and abstraction (Milad, 2017).

Blended learning from an educational concept perspective combines the focus of teaching and learning. Powell et al. (2015) stated that students have maximum control over their own learning materials, location, and time. In other words, blended learning is a combination of both types of learning, as traditional face-to-face presentations and online lessons are used in the teaching and learning process. This creates more learning opportunities that motivate students to participate both in and out of class. From the perspective of the classroom environment, the concepts of static state and Internet access are considered. This is in line with Sivapunniam (2009) who emphasized that in addition to various aspects of online learning, blended learning includes several elements of traditional education such as: direct instructions, demonstrations, monitoring, etc. In another definition, Sharma (2010) argued that technology includes online classes, advanced whiteboards, and language labs, among others.

The purpose of this study is to review previous research on blended learning regarding approaches and implementation of blended learning strategies in order to consider the challenges in implementing it.

Literature Review

The Positive Perceptions towards Blended Learning

Several studies have been conducted on blended learning, which combines online and face-to-face learning. These studies show that learning and technology should be closely related (Camahalan & Ruley, 2014). It indicated that blended learning approach accelerates teaching and learning process. That is considered as a technique to employ technology in the educational process to reach the highest potential success of education.

Blended learning gives educators easy access to a wide range of devices and resources to meet the educational needs of learners. It also helps educators address the issue of time constraints in the classroom. A variety of assessment tools and test formats are provided to allow teachers to prepare different tests for different educational purposes.

One of the studies that vouches for the effectiveness of classroom learning and online learning is the study conducted by Tehrani and Tabatabaie (2012). This study analyzed the effects of blended learning and face-to-face instruction on Iranian learners' vocabulary success. The results of this study prove that the blended learning approach contributes to improving learners' vocabulary knowledge. They believed this would provide more genuine, real-world opportunities for learners to use the language both inside and outside of the classroom.

Ju & Mei (2018) conducted a study to determine the reasons why English teachers use Blended Learning and its related materials and the tools in their classrooms. Research instruments used in the study were a questionnaire and the interviews to elicit the teachers' viewpoint regarding this approach. The results showed that teachers reflected positive perception toward blended learning. They also maintained that having effective and productive blended teaching requires that instructors should be equipped with higher personal proficiency in computer skills.

In their study, Namaziandost et al. (2020) conducted a questionnaire survey whose goal was to determine the English learners' beliefs about blended learning. Results proved that learners had a receptive attitude about the blended learning. Researches done by Mohammadi et al. (2019) and Hajebe (2020) confirmed this concept that learners experiencing blended approach showed more willingness and motivation toward learning. Chansamrong et al. (2014) displayed effective relation between blended learning and comprehending grammar. The participants were the students who experienced learning grammar under blended-cooperative instruction and gained a better score. A survey given to the students displayed that the participants reflected great attitudes towards learning English grammar using blended learning.

In their study about learners' attitudes of a blended learning instruction, Wang et al., (2009) asserted that activities can draw students' attention effectively in the blended learning process. Therefore, learners in this kind of instruction are not passive learners but truly active learners who are cognitively engaged in the learning activities. This was further confirmed by Emelyanova and Voronina (2017) who asserted that the blended learning approach is much better in accelerating self-paced learning and students' powerful incentive.

Tools of Blended Learning

Many tools are available to be used in creating effective blended learning. Wang (2010) mentioned that the implementing blended learning tools in higher level learning contexts improves participation and communication among learners and thus gives rise to a higher level of learner-centered atmosphere. Higgins and Gomez (2014) gave five categories of the suggested tools abstracted from Allan (2007, pp. 15-45).

“A. Classroom technologies used in such as PowerPoint, interactive whiteboards and audience response systems.

B. Virtual communication tools such as audio files, discussion boards, e-lists, discussion groups, chat or conferencing, email, news groups, polling, questionnaires, web forms and video conferencing.

C. Social-networking software such as instant messaging and phone calls, podcasts, social-networking sites, video clips, virtual worlds, weblogs and wikis.

D. E-learning systems such as VLEs (Virtual Learning Environments), conferencing systems, group collaboration software and group sites and mobile learning using mobile phones, laptops and tablet PCs.”

Blended Learning and Language Skills

The ultimate goal of teaching English is mastering the language skills and components involving reading, listening, speaking, writing, grammar and vocabulary to help the learner address real-life situations. Many studies established this point that blended learning approach assists learners to improve their language proficiency and skills. Several studies have confirmed a significant relationship between implementation of e-learning in the language classroom and the achievement of better language skills. The effect of blended learning has been proven to be effective in improving foreign language skills (Rivera, 2019). Blended Learning approach allows educators to offer systematic instruction that aims at focusing on every student’s skill needs and can increase the efficient amount of time spent in educational contexts (Kazakoff et al., 2018).

The Effects of Blended Learning on Reading Comprehension

Reading is considered as a language skill that ought to be accomplished by the student to reach the ultimate objectives of learning a language. The skill of reading is known as a receptive not productive language skill. Reading comprehension is characterized as information processing which means that the learner ought to have the capacity to encode and decode a written text to grasp the materials. Certainly, the repeated use of the Internet will motivate learners to do reading to a great extent. A standard online reading involvement lets learners achieve higher level of reading comprehension assignments such as summary writing, rewording, drawing deductions and engaging with online interactive tools such as an email writing or producing a blog post (Hashemi & Na, 2020).

Several studies have investigated the effects of blended learning on the students' reading comprehension. The procedure used by Behjat et al. (2011) was that the control group students were asked to read and study the printed texts outside of the class and summarize them, whereas the students in the experimental group were asked to visit an online weblog after class to find their reading assignments. It was assumed that the weekly reading tasks would be posted by the participants on the blog. It should be noted that although all students in the control and experimental groups received research treatment in their out-of-class activities, they all took classroom reading in a traditional face-to-face instructional format lasting for two and a half months, two hours a week.

The reading material posted on the teachers' weblogs was exactly the same as the printed materials assigned to the control group. Three different texts of the same difficulty level were posted every week. Using a learner-centered approach, the researchers asked participants to select a topic of their choice, read and summarize related texts. The reading texts were available in wiki format. This means that there are several links that participants can click to access further reading material on a particular term used in texts on other websites, and the reading texts also had sections that participants could edit if they wanted to add material to the text for others to read. In fact, a notable feature of Wiki pages is that they have links to other websites and can be edited. Participants were asked to discuss, exchange ideas, and have interactions about the reading theme. Researchers found that reading comprehension

tasks in electronic tools such as Wikis provide links that allow learners to simply click on an underlined term or phrase to go to a new web page and access a variety of reading comprehension resources. They concluded that blended learning increases learners' autonomy to read more material than is presented in the classroom.

In a study on the use of blended learning to develop reading comprehension skills, Kheirzadeh and Bahrami (2018) conducted a treatment in which the experimental group read passages from the book "Select Readings" during ten 90-minute sessions of the study. They also had to use nicenet.com at home. On the other hand, for the control group, the passages were taught in the classroom based on a traditional teaching approach, and the content, instructions, and feedback were presented in the classroom based on the book "Select Readings." This website serves as a virtual class for the experimental group. The website allowed teachers to create virtual classes and give students a password to join them. In this virtual class, the teacher posted the passage three times a week, and participants had to practice the passage through various tasks such as discussion, problem solving, fill-in-the-blank, comprehension questions, and story completion. The teacher corrected the participants' mistakes, and the participants used the teacher's comments and feedback online. This process continued until the end of the semester, with all participants in the experimental group using this website three times a week. They concluded that blended learning had a positive and significant effect on Iranian EFL students' reading comprehension. This finding highlights the importance and importance of blended learning in language acquisition.

Kheirzadeh and Bahrami (2018) argue that blended learning pedagogically addresses different learning needs and leads to the development of individualized learning designs for learners. This allows learners to improve their skills by blending the virtual world with their own learning during class, as well as their ability to perform independently in blended learning after class.

Similarly, Elahi and Mashhadi Heidar (2021) investigated the use of blended learning in English reading comprehension courses. In the treatment group's reading course, students were taught through blended integrated language learning. The total treatment period for both experimental groups was 1 month (4 sessions per week), with 90 minutes spent on treatment per session. The blended learning treatment involves engaging learners in interactive tasks and activities previously created by researchers through the TedEd website (ed.ted.com). First, students watched a video about "Data Visualization with David McCandless." They then answered two analytical questions and discussed their answers with their partner. They then visited McCandless's website (informationisBeautiful.net) and found an infographic that they found particularly interesting and effective to share with the class.

In a further stage, the learners were divided into small groups. The teacher then gave each group a project. These projects were designed by researchers using Goformative.com. Teachers posted various reading passages on the website, and each group was assigned a different reading topic. Each online task consists of three parts. In the first part, learners watched a National Geographic video to familiarize themselves with the topic. They then read a passage online and answered an online multiple-choice question at the end.

Teachers provided a traditional reading instruction routine to the control group, and the control group received 16 consecutive sessions of regular laboratory reading instruction for 90 minutes per session. The findings of Elahi and Mashhadi Heidar (2021) suggest that traditional paper-based approaches to reading comprehension are no longer adopted by learners. Learners are then no longer limited to reading large amounts of text, and the reading process usually becomes boring, thus students become bored and become passive learners. Learners had a more positive attitude toward reading when they were asked to study lessons and complete tasks provided in videos from ed.ted.com, goformative.com, and TED Talks. Additionally, teachers design and create evaluative and analytical reading-based online assignments that promote learners' critical thinking skills.

The Effects of Blended Learning on Listening

Nowadays, listening practice is mainly carried out in classrooms, and although most teachers consider listening as a basic skill (Soodmand Afshar & Hamzavi, 2014), listening skills have not received enough attention. It appears that the learners are not sufficiently trained technological and learner-centered instructional approaches.

Vaezi et al. (2019) investigated the impact of blended learning on improving listening performance. During this study, the control group received traditional classroom instruction in a teacher-centered learning environment, with the same amount of time and activity for them scaffolding tasks, except that responses to listening comprehension tasks were completed at home. However, the experimental group learned differently because the lesson content was taught in advance to give students the opportunity to learn at their own pace. The researchers emailed the screencasts, PowerPoint files, and audio materials they created to the participants. Participants will carefully study the material that will help participants in the experimental group prepare for the purpose of the class in line with the objectives of the course, rather than theoretical explanations on how to meet and improve the IELTS listening comprehension requirements more independently.

Hussein Alsowayegh et al. (2019) asserted that their online learning environment was in Blackboard®. Blackboard is considered a web-based course management system designed to allow students and instructors to take courses offered online and to supplement in-person instruction with online materials and activities. Blackboard allows students to create, upload, and share videos with their teacher or class. Videos allow students to focus more on learning by requiring them to create and synthesize information. Researchers place content online that students can interact with asynchronously, improve students' ability to consider where and when they choose to engage online, and support learning materials in a safe and personalized environment.

Before each face-to-face session, the teacher asked students to access the link on Blackboard® and complete the activity. Students were also tested using the Blackboard® quiz tool to help them guess and understand what was expected of them in individual sessions through online activities. Before starting the listening practice, the teacher had to provide the necessary background knowledge, such as cultural and vocabulary content. The teacher provided a link to an online video via Blackboard® and asked students to identify the vocabulary. Research results showed that students who experienced blended learning achieved higher engagement.

The Effects of Blended Learning on Speaking

Shih (2010) investigated the use of blended learning with video-based blogs in English classes and showed that students were highly satisfied with the blended learning program. He found that a blended learning model with video-based blogging could be an effective approach for learners to learn public speaking productively and efficiently. Shih (2010) stated that blended learning helps learners develop language skills such as pronunciation, grammar, eye contact, and facial expressions.

Ginaya et al., (2018) described a structured attempt to examine the impact of blended learning on learners' speaking ability through the application of Web Quest project tasks added to a modified traditional teaching model. The results showed that learners who experienced blended learning significantly improved their English skills. The study used two types of instruments, one of which records the student's performance in a given activity, such as a teaching journal and observation sheets, and the other instrument was in the form of tests and questionnaires. Both the experimental and control groups received two educational sessions during the first week. The materials used in the lessons were from the books given to the students, the learning method was mainly deductive, and the topic discussion was modified into a chronological sequence of presentations, practice, and communication activities. The treatment period was 3 weeks, during which the experimental group received

researcher-designed Web Quests (web-based activities) as project assignments through e-learning via the Edmodo network. Each task in the Web Quest project was completed within three days and submitted based on Edmodo's task submission deadlines. In subsequent lessons, students practiced speaking activities using a modified teaching model consisting of communication activities, practice, and presentations.

The control group was given only the traditional teaching model described in the textbook. This teaching model was created with a chronological sequence of presentations, practices, and communication activities without the supplementation of Web Quest. The improvements achieved by students here are also supported by the fact that applying Web Quest's Active Learning activities can increase students' motivation and interest in learning. This allows for active interaction throughout the learning process.

Ehsanifard et al. (2004) tried to investigate whether blended learning has a significant impact on the language proficiency of Iranian learners. The researchers used the Nicenet platform. This allows teachers to easily share links and documents under the mentioned topic headings, as well as conduct discussions via the conferencing feature on Nicenet. The experimental group used the Nicenet platform in such a way that the teacher registered on the Nicenet and asked participants in the experimental group to register on the www.Nicenet.org and join the class. The teacher presented the conference topic and sent the material to the learners via Nicenet. In the virtual classroom, the teacher created participants' schemas through a series of questions about the topic. Attempts were made to use real texts such as television advertisements, music, videos, political texts, and images as topics of conversation. Participants are responsible for understanding the topic of conversation and the overall situation while listening. Next, the learners were asked general questions about the conversation.

If the answer was incorrect, the peers were asked to provide an answer. The learners were then asked to listen again and ask probing questions about the conversation. The teacher developed the necessary vocabulary and structures by giving clear instructions and also providing examples. Finally, participants worked in pairs to exchange documents and links with each other and practice speaking. At the end of the session, a discussion about the theme of the lesson was developed in an individual way. Teachers participated in this activity to provide feedback and continue the conversation. Ehsanifard et al. (2020) found that participants in a mixed group improved their overall oral skills more than the group that took a traditional course. Blended format gives learners of different personality types the opportunity to progress at their own pace.

The Effects of Blended Learning on Writing

Although writing as a basic language skill is one of the main goals of foreign language learning (Vakili & Ebadi, 2019), this skill is considered to be the most demanding language skill that EFL learners need to learn (Du, 2020; Jabali, 2018). Keili et al. (2019) wanted to investigate the impact of the web-integrated instruction on self-regulated learning ability in EFL writing. They also compare and contrast the effects of paper-based and web-based feedback on self-regulated learning abilities. In their quantitative quasi-experimental study, they provided the experimental group with a type of web-integrated and blended learning treatment throughout the semester.

Before treatment, students' interest in web-based learning was stimulated through teachers' explanations, clear instructions, and guidelines about the benefits of the web in language learning. Students were asked to check the online site before each session and before answering the teacher's questions. All lessons in this study were presented in the form of available online forums, but these were primarily used for one-sided communication by the teacher. Students were also required to use online forums to communicate with each other. Teachers in the experimental group facilitated online

contact with students through forums. Each session also included an online test on vocabulary and structures related to the writing activity. All these online quizzes, online writing assignments, and forums kept this participation online for most of the semester. Students posted relevant materials online, participated in online study groups, and provided peer feedback on writing course topics.

Dousti and Amirian (2022) aimed to compare the effectiveness of web-mediated blended instruction on learners' writing performance in the Iranian context. The experimental group was provided with online sessions as well as classroom sessions where learners were required to participate in the course. The class was divided into several sessions, the purpose of which was to teach learners the basics of how to write the web quests and argumentative essays. The third and fifth sessions were again held online using Adobe Connect as the virtual learning platform. The instructor then provided relevant web quests and divided the class into smaller groups using Adobe Connect's "breakout rooms" feature. If there were any problems, the instructor guided the learners online. The learner will be required to submit her five-paragraph essay work at the end of each session, which will be considered post-test.

Researchers found that using Web Quest tasks facilitated the learning process, especially in writing skills and subskills. They argued that if blended learning is properly implemented, education can move from a primarily "knowledge transfer" approach to content delivery to a more "knowledge construction" approach.

Torabi (2021) investigated the impact of blended learning via Google Classroom on Iranian EFL learners' writing accuracy. Google Classroom is a free blended learning platform designed by Google for educational institutions to make it easy to create, distribute, and grade assignments. According to Iftakhar (2016), Google Classroom is a free product that allows quick connectivity with other Google devices such as Gmail, Google Drive, and Google Docs. Furthermore, Google Classroom facilitates communication between learners and between teachers and learners as the app provides a single point of access to assigned assignments and discussions (Heggart & Yoo, 2018).

The researcher introduced Google Classroom to the learners in the experimental group and conducted 20 sessions of classes based on blended learning. Learners are encouraged to search the internet for relevant information about Google Classroom and share it with others. The learner also received instructions on how and where to find relevant materials and assignments posted to the Google Classroom by the teachers and classmates, and how to provide feedback on the peers' writing. After providing learners with the necessary guidelines for using and working with Google Classroom, learners were given a writing topic for each session and asked to write and post a paragraph to the Google Classroom.

Before performing the task, the teacher taught the necessary grammar and vocabulary related to the task. This is followed by questions and exercises to ensure that learners understand the task, relevant vocabulary, and grammar. Learners post their writing to the Google Classroom and help each other revise their drafts. After each Google Classroom session, the researchers attempted to participate in the class. Before class, learners print out their essays and receive feedback on their essays through pair and group work in the classroom by working together to make a list of mistakes and correcting them on paper. During the discussion phase, the teacher asked each pair or group of learners to write difficult errors on the board and discuss the mistake individually as a whole-class activity.

Therefore, learners wrote their first drafts during Google Classroom sessions, but did not receive detailed feedback on writing errors, and derived initial and final revisions through group work and discussion during face-to-face sessions. In the control group, the researcher presented the material face-to-face in a traditional manner over the 20 sessions, and the learners were asked to submit their texts in the next session.

Conclusion

The findings and experiences reflected in this study indicate that blended learning has a positive impact on English language teaching and learning. As education increasingly moves towards online and blended learning formats, it makes sense to give due consideration to the judicious combination of online and face-to-face educational elements in the learning process. Teachers can use the results and experiences of this study to apply such meaningful integration practices in their classroom environments, and educators and practitioners can use the results and experiences of this study to develop appropriate technology bases for use in ESL teaching and learning. Several related studies were conducted to examine the impact of using blended learning in teaching and learning on the acquisition of the four integrated skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing) of English. This review confirmed the positive effects of using blended learning in improving English language skills. By implementing a blended learning program, learners can gain skills such as communication, problem solving, innovation, and technology expertise.

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